

NANODEFORMATION BEHAVIOUR AND STRAIN DISTRIBUTION IN Ti ALLOY MATRIX COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

Various nanoscale deformation modes including slip bands, surface roughening, cracking of whiskers and particles are observed during tensile loading. The degree of local deformation varied at different locations due to inhomogeneous microstructures. High strain concentration areas were found to be near the whisker end and near the whisker cracking site.

Keywords: Nanodeformation, Strain measurement, In-situ AFM, Nanolithography, Ti Composite

ABSTRACT

The nanoscopic local deformation behaviour of a TiC particle and TiB whisker reinforced Ti-6-4 alloy matrix composite during tensile loading was investigated by in-situ Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) with patterning technique. To understand nanodeformation and fracture mechanisms, local deformation and strain were measured and analysed using digital images obtained before and after straining. The strain distribution around the reinforcements and the whisker and the particle cracking site during tensile loading will be discussed using in-situ AFM observation.

1. Introduction

Discontinuously reinforced titanium composites containing TiB and/or TiC are emerging as promising materials for advanced aerospace and automobile applications [1-5]. The composite have been shown to have attractive combinations of strength, Young's modulus, fracture toughness, excellent creep and fatigue resistance [4,5]. It is well known that the matrix properties and the reinforcement volume fraction, shape, size, spatial distribution, etc. play an important role in determining the composite strength and ductility [5,6]. The damage and fracture processes in discontinuously reinforced composites have been studied by various experimental techniques, such as in-situ scanning electron microscopy [7,8], X-ray tomography [9], the elastic modulus

degradation [10]. These investigations showed that the damage mechanisms during deformation were mainly formation and growth of voids at the matrix/reinforcement interface and fracture of the reinforcement. The fracture of the reinforcement has been proposed through a stress criterion based on the Weibull statistics attributed to the defect distribution present [11]. The effect of matrix deformation on failure mechanism for the reinforcement in the metallic matrix during tensile loading has not been experimentally investigated.

Atomic force microscope (AFM) is a powerful tool to analyze the characteristics of three-dimensional surface features with nanometer dimensions. AFM has been used to observe slip bands produced by static and fatigue loading; and to study the mechanisms of fatigue crack initiation and damage evolution in several different metallic alloys including aluminum, copper, titanium and stainless steels [12-17]. Using in-situ AFM instead of in-situ SEM observation has several advantages: (i) both in-plane and out-of-plane deformation can be evaluate simultaneously at the nanoscale resolution, (ii) the experiments are carried out in ambient condition without vacuum, (iii) the electrical conductivity for materials is not necessary. The evolution of surface roughness and slip band spacing during tensile loading was quantified, and the effect of matrix plasticity deformation on the reinforcement was investigated. A few articles demonstrated the three dimensional strain fields measured by AFM on patterned composite specimen by means of the microelectric-lithography technique with 5 μm distance.

In the present study, direct observation in discontinuously reinforced Ti composite during tensile loading was conducted by an in-situ AFM observation. The local deformation measurement method has been established by means of nanolithographic technique. These observations are discussed to underline the mechanisms for reinforcement breaks significances of matrix plasticity evolution.

2. Experimental Procedure

2.1. Composite Material

The composite material used in this study was an in-situ TiC and TiB reinforced Ti-6Al-4V composite produced by Crucible Research LLC (Pittsburgh, PA). The composition of the alloy was Ti-6Al-4V-1.1B-0.8C (all in weight percent). The pre-alloyed powder reinforced with TiB and TiC was produced by adding boron and carbon to a titanium alloy melt via induction skull melting followed by inert-gas atomization. The atomized powder was consolidated using hot isostatic pressing (HIPing) at 1000 °C followed by extrusion at 1095 °C into a plate. A typical example of the polished extruded section of the composite is shown in Figure 1. The sample was cut directly from the extruded bar and was

Figure 1 A typical example of the polished extruded section of the composite.

polished and etched with a solution of water, nitric acid, and hydrofluoric acid in proportions of 85:10:5. The microstructure consists of TiB whiskers with diameters ranging from 0.2 to 3 μm , and the equiaxed TiC particles with diameters ranging from 3-5 μm . The effect of extrusion in aligning the TiB whisker in the direction of extrusion is apparent. The volume fraction of TiB whisker and TiC particle in the composite is close to 5.5 and 4 %, respectively. The particles presented irregular shapes, with sharp corners, and were usually oriented with their longer axis in the extruded direction.

2-2. In-situ Observation

The specimens for in-situ tensile tests were prepared using electrical discharge machining method with loading parallel to the extruded direction. The central parts of the specimens has a dog-bone shape with a width of 2.5 mm and a thickness of 1.2 mm. To allow a direct observation of damage progression, one surface of the specimen was progressively polished with diamond paste up to 0.25 μm , and was finally polished with a solution of MASTERMET (Buehler, Ltd.) which has a SiO₂ particle size of 60 nm in an aqueous base (10 pH), hydrogen peroxide, and ammonia water of 92:4:4. The experimental set-up for in-situ AFM observation during tensile loading is shown in Figure 2. A special loading device was built to fit in the AFM (AutoProbe M5, Nihon Veeco Corp.). The maximum loading capacity is 2000 N. The load increment was controlled precisely by a stepping motor.

Prior to the in-situ tensile test, AFM nanolithography technique was used to introduce grating pattern on the polished surface to facilitate direct observation of local deformation state. Initially, a gold film of 30 nm in thickness was evaporated onto the specimen surface using ion coater (IB-5, EIKO Engineering Co., Ltd). Gold film was selected primarily because the hardness of gold (Hv: 20) is much lower than the silicon cantilever (Hv: 800) and having higher deformability, thus surface nanodamage can be avoided. An array of parallel lines with 500 nm spacing were drawn onto the specimen surface perpendicular to the loading direction by means of a nanolithographic technique with a contact mode of AFM. Scratching into gold film by the silicon cantilever with a scratch velocity of 1mm/s and the maximum normal load of 0.05mN was used in this study. A cantilever (Ultralever, Thermo Microscope Corp.) fabricated from silicon with a spring constant of 1.6 N/m and a tip radius of 15 nm was used for nanolithography.

A strain gauge was also mounted on the back side of the specimen to record the elongation during tensile loading. The test was conducted at a cross-head speed of 0.01 mm/min. The loading was stopped after a predetermined amount of strain increment to allow AFM observation of surface. The tip was scanned across a small surface area to sample the surface topography with a non-contact mode at a

Figure 2 Experimental set-up for in-situ AFM observation with a special loading device.

frequency of 320 KHz, and a resolution of 512×512 pixels. To minimize creep deformation in air during in-situ AFM observation, the specimen was unloaded to the elastic deformation region (around 500 MPa). The surface roughness profiles and surface average roughness amplitude, R_a , were analyzed by built-in software. The optical microscope equipped with a CCD camera was used to find the appropriate mark on the center of the specimen. The fracture surface was examined by a scanning electron microscope.

3. Results and discussion

The composite has a yield strength of 1200 MPa and an ultimate tensile strength of 1400 MPa. The incorporation of TiB whiskers and TiC particles would improve the yield and tensile strength of Ti-6Al-4V significantly. However, the ductility of the composite was measured to be around 7 %, which is somewhat lower than that of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy. Observation of fracture surface of the composite by Scanning Electron Microscope indicates strong whisker/matrix interfacial strength because the dimple pattern in Ti-6Al-4V matrix along with rupture of the reinforcements and no pull-out of TiB whiskers was clearly observed.

The evolution of surface morphology with the error signal image observed using in-situ AFM in the region of $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$ under three different strain levels, $\epsilon_c = 0.8$, 1.9 and 4.7 % are shown in Figure 3. In the surface morphology image, the TiB and TiC reinforcements on the surface can be clearly seen before straining. The higher amplitude of TiC particles is approximately 80 nm higher than other region suggests that the

Figure 3 The evolution of surface morphology and the error signal image of the composite reinforced with TiC particle and TiB whisker observed under a AFM at three different strain levels: (a) and (a') $\epsilon_c = 0.8\%$, (b) and (b') $\epsilon_c = 1.9\%$, (c) and (c') $\epsilon_c = 4.7\%$.

Figure 4 The evolution of surface morphology and the error signal image at a high magnification of the boxed region B in Figure 3(c) : (a) and (a') $\epsilon_c = 0.8\%$, (b) and (b') $\epsilon_c = 4.7\%$, (c) and (c'): detail observation of the boxed region in (b).

surface roughness is strongly affected by the hardness of materials during mechanical polishing process. The details of damage evolution such as cracking of whisker and particle or matrix slip bands with increasing the strain is obscured due to the presence of large surface roughness. The error signal image can resolve the details of such damage events, as indicated by (a'), (b') and (c') in the figures, respectively. It is clearly showed that the evolution of surface roughness was increased with increasing applied strain. Figure 4 shows a high magnification (measured area of $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$) of the boxed region B in Figure 3(c). As shown in figure 4(a), no slip band was observed at a strain level of 0.8 %, since it is still within the elastic deformation regime. As the applied strain was increased to beyond the elastic range, slip bands were observed at a strain level of 1.3%. When the applied strain was further increased to 4.7%, localized deformation at the whisker end (as indicated by black arrows in figure 4(b')) and a significant amount of slip bands were clearly observed as shown in Figures 4(b) and (b'). Observation of the SEM back scatter

Figure 5 Relative surface roughness profiles of a line in Figure 4(b) based on various step of different applied strain.

electron imaging (BSEI) revealed that the microstructure of the matrix was identified equiaxed a-phase and intergranular b-phase. The formation of slip bands initiated within individual a-phase grain was increased with the orientation of the slip system in the grain. At the high magnification (in figure 4(b)) of the interaction between slip bands and TiB whisker, the multiple fracture of TiB whisker is clearly observed near the slip bands as indicated by white arrows in the figure 4(c'). It appears that when a shear slip band intersects a TiB whisker, the stress concentration due to dislocation pile-up may cause the shear and/or tensile failure of the whisker. It has been showed that the fracture of discontinuous fiber by slip bands plays a significant role in the damage evolution process of the composite. Figure 5 shows the surface roughness profiles of a line in Figure 4(b) based on various step of different applied strain. It is clearly shown that the localized deformation at the point of A and B near the whisker ends were found to increase with increasing applied strain. These differences suggest that the localized surface plastic deformation is significantly affected by local events such microstructural inhomogeneity and anisotropy, size and distribution of the reinforcements, reinforcement cracking, slip bands formation and interfacial shear strength.

A typical example of the surface morphology after making the grating on the specimen surface observed by AFM (measured area: $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$) is shown in Figure 6. Horizontal direction is the loading direction in the figure. The grating spacing of the gold film was

clearly observed on the specimen surface. The parallel lines formed by the AFM nanolithography were locally distorted from the original line, especially at the whisker end and near the ruptured whisker (indicated by white arrows in Figure 6(c) and (d)). Average local strain distribution could be calculated based on position changes of selected grids between applied strain increments. Figure 7 shows the strain contour map in a selected area ($8.5 \times 7.0 \mu\text{m}$) shown in Figure 7 at an applied strain of $\epsilon_c = 4.6\%$. The

Figure 6 The evolution of surface morphology before and after straining in the region containing TiB whiskers: (a) before straining, (b) after straining of 4.6%, (c) and (d) detail of region A and B in (b), respectively.

measured strain distribution along the loading axis was found to be in the range of 0.7 ~ 22.9%. Obviously, the degree of local deformation varied at different locations due to heterogeneous and inhomogeneous microstructures. For example, the average axial tensile strain in the matrix on the right side of the whisker end was determined to be 22.9%, which is 5 times larger than the applied strain of 4.57%, while the average axial strain was determined to be 0.7% at the center of the whisker. Moreover, the average axial strain of 18.1% was found in the lower left region, which was induced by the fracture of TiB whisker. As the rupture of whisker occurred, the load carried by the whisker would be released to the neighboring matrix, resulting in a much higher strain level. The results clearly demonstrate that the AFM coupled with nanolithography is a useful tool for observing the surface morphology and measuring the local deformation around the reinforcements such as whiskers with a nanometer resolution.

Figure 7 The strain contour map along the loading direction at an applied strain of 4.75 %..

4. Summary

The nanoscopic local deformation behavior of a TiC particle and TiB whisker reinforced Ti-6-4 alloy matrix composite during tensile loading was investigated by in-situ AFM observation coupled with nanolithography. Various nanoscale deformation modes including slip bands, surface roughening, cracking and distortio/re-orientation of whiskers are observed during tensile loading. The amount of slip bands and the average surface roughness were found to increase with increasing applied strain due to plastic deformation in the matrix through the formation of matrix slip bands. The matrix slip bands create sharp discontinuities on the order of 5-15 nm at the surface of TiB whisker that may cause the stress concentration, cracking and distortion of TiB whisker. The multiple fracture of TiB whisker is, therefore, a synergistic effect of both the stress transfer mechanism and the stress concentration mechanism due to the presence of slip bands.

The distortion of the nanolithographic grids and its corresponding strain contour were measured and analyzed. At an applied strain of 4.6%, the measured strain distribution along the loading axis was found to be in the range of 0.7 ~ 22.9%. The degree of local deformation varied at different locations due to heterogeneous and inhomogeneous microstructures. High strain concentration areas were found to be near the whisker end and near the whisker cracking site.

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